

PRIME SPORTS FM COVERAGE AND ENUGU RANGERS PERFORMANCE IN THE 2024 NIGERIA PREMIER FOOTBALL LEAGUE

Agbo, Amaechi Vitus

Department of Mass Communication

Enugu State University of Science and Technology

Abstract

The broad objectives of the study were to examine the influence of Prime Sports FM Coverage on Enugu Rangers Performance in the 2024 Nigeria Premier Football League. The specific objectives were to: find out the influence of coverage given by 104.9 Prime Sports FM during Enugu Rangers' physical strength in 2024 NPFL season and ascertain the level of influence of social media instruments used by 104.9 Prime Sports FM during Enugu Rangers' speed in 2024 NPFL campaign. Convergent mixed-method research design was deployed such as survey, unstructured interview, and Focus Group Discussion were utilized. Total population of the study was 267,837. Sample size of study was three hundred and eighty-four (384) using Freund and William's statistics formula. Stratified sampling technique was adopted for selecting the respondents that completed the questionnaire. After data analysis, it was found that there was significant positive level of coverage given by 104.9 Prime Sports FM on physical strength during Enugu Rangers' 2024 NPFL campaign ($Z = 20.548$, $n = 346$, $.000 < 0.05$) and there was significant positive level of social media instruments used by Prime Sports FM on speed during Enugu Rangers' 2024 NPFL season. It was concluded that Prime Sports FM's coverage had significant positive influence on Rangers International FC performance. Therefore, it was recommended that Prime Sports FM should open up more vistas for mass media participation while ensuring that the sports development policy would include creating more outlets for generating revenue through sports by organising more sports competitions as well as establishing more recreational outlets at the local government levels and Prime Sports FM Enugu should continue using social media instruments as tradition pattern since, it helps in passing information or awareness across Nigeria by adopting Facebook, WhatsApp, X, Instagram, etc.

Keywords: Prime Sports FM Coverage, Enugu Rangers Performance, Level of Coverage, Social Media Instruments

Introduction

On June 16, 2024, Enugu Rangers Football Club won the 2023/2024 Nigeria Premier Football League (NPFL) after defeating Bendel Insurance 2-0 at the Nnamdi Azikiwe Stadium, Enugu with a game to spare. However, the team, also regarded as the Flying Antelopes, were crowned Champions of the NPFL season in Jos on Sunday, June 23rd, 2024 after beating Gombe United 2-1 in the final league match day 38 encounter. While the good people of Enugu State and South East region were in ecstasy over this huge triumph, a section of the people was angered, felt disregarded and disconnected from the team's success - sports journalists in Enugu.

Working under the Sports Writers Association of Nigeria (SWAN), the journalists felt aggrieved that despite their "immense role" in Enugu Rangers winning the title, their eighth thus far, they (the sports journalists) were not accorded the needed respect and regards they deserved. Members of the group felt that Rangers management neglected them and therefore vowed to boycott coverage of the club's league matches and activities. They alleged that while their colleagues in Enugu were disregarded, Rangers

management paid for at least four sports journalists in Lagos (who through flight) arrived at the Jos Township Stadium, venue of the final league match, to cover the encounter against Gombe United (Yta, *et al.*, 2020; Enos, 2022).

Their dispositions, were further aggravated when the Enugu State Governor, Dr Peter Ndubuisi Mbah hosted the triumphant Enugu Rangers team, management and officials to a banquet at the Government House in Enugu. Again, the sports journalists were not considered for invitation. The Governor at the dinner party, gave the team N50, 000 000 as reward for their exploits. SWAN members in Enugu vowed that they would have nothing to do with the club going forward. Although they expressed these grievances on their WhatsApp platform, the Chairman of the group, Comrade Gideon Iweke however appealed to the members to give the leadership of the group a chance to look into the situation (Yta, *et al.*, 2020; Enos, 2022).

This researcher, being a member of the SWAN Enugu State Chapter, was then triggered to embark on investigations on the impact of the media in sports development and also to determine if actually the SWAN members had any influence or impact in Enugu Rangers/Rangers International Football Club winning the 2023/2024 NPFL trophy (Yta & Umukoro, 2018).

The primary objective of any media is to communicate something to the target audience to expand its periphery of visibility. The relationship between sports and mass media is intimate because the media not only carve public opinion but also help propagate it, thus promoting sporting events. Social media, sports broadcasting, sports journalism, and sports coverage influence and shape public perception of sports. One may start liking a sport just because of the hype that it has gained. One is even made aware of the various sports that they do not know of and athletes that they have not heard of before because of how mass media increase the popularity of sports. *Gokhale Institute of Politics & Economics, June 30, 2023.*

Statement of the Problem

Apart from the fact that the media have increased sports awareness, conduct mass mobilization, entertainment values, information dissemination, news presentation, education process, and spectatorship among peoples of the world, it has also increased revenue generation which has enriched the various sports stakeholders. The media have been playing a catalyst role for the identification and promotion of knowledge, information and understanding about various aspects of sports and sporting talents in various nations. Pointed out those competitive sports would only survive and develop with the cooperation of the media. It is for this reason that sports must enjoy good relationship with the press, radio, and television. The relationship should be effective, continuous, personal and open (Morakinyo).

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to examine the influence of Prime Sports FM's coverage on Rangers' international FC performance in the 2024 Nigeria Premier Football League. The specific objectives were to;

- i. Find out the influence of coverage given by 104.9 Prime Sports FM during Enugu Rangers' physical strength in 2024 NPFL season.
- ii. Ascertain the level of influence of social media instruments used by 104.9 Prime Sports FM during Enugu Rangers' speed in 2024 NPFL campaign.

Review of Related Literature

Prime Sports FM

104.9 Prime Sports FM is a Sports and entertainment radio birthed to meet the yearning demands of people of the South-East Nigeria with a mission to provide premium quality programming in sports and entertainment across multiple platforms laced on ethical standards of global best practice. Prime Sports FM was founded on the need to breach the gap between reporting Nigeria's local sports contents and that of the European sphere. The station covers the South-East and its environs. The station started transmission in 2021 providing information and updates especially on sports with their target audience being the youths, youthful at heart and upward mobile executives. The researcher interviewed the General Manager of Prime Sports FM, Okechukwu Odogwu who laid bare the reason for establishing the radio station in 2021 and the impact it is making in sports casting not just in Enugu but in the South East region.

“Sport refers to a playful self-development, self-actualization, and competitive use of physical and mental skills. The history of sports activities is as long as the history of humans. Fitness played an important role in human evolution. For example, hunting, one of the main adaptive problems in evolutionary history, requires physical fitness and good teamwork. For hunters, these qualities meant more and/or better food; better and/or more food meant better chances in the battle for survival. Good physical, mental, and social shape improved the chances to successfully protect groups and tribes from other groups of aggressive intruders. Because of this connection, we can say that the first sportsmen were hunters and soldiers. Indeed, there are strong theories of sports being symbolic hunts, either for other humans or for animals” (Drapo, *et al.* 2021).

Level of Coverage

Coverage areas of broadcast stations can be classified into primary, secondary and fringe areas. The size of each of these coverage areas depends on the transmitter power, the directivity of the antenna, the height of antenna above the earth's surface, the ground electrical conductivity and the frequency of propagation. The coverage areas decrease with increase in frequency and reduction in the ground conductivity (Ajayi and Owolabi, 2019).

Level of Social Media Instruments

Kaplan and Haenlein (2020), social media is internet-based applications that allow the creation and exchange of content which is user generated. The internet and in particular social media applications such as Twitter, yahoo messenger, Facebook messenger, WhatsApp messenger, Skype, 2go messenger, google talk, google messenger, YouTube and many others, are obviously “overtaking the world” and could be regarded as “a global consumer phenomenon” (Camilia, Ibrahim, & Dalhatu, 2023).

Sports Programmers

Sports participation in Nigeria is a multifaceted concept that encompasses various aspects of engagements in organized physical activities. It includes both formal and informal sports involvement among individuals of different age groups, genders, and socio-cultural backgrounds. Understanding the dynamics and factors related to sport participation in Nigeria is crucial for promoting physical fitness, social integration, and overall well-being among the population.

Responsibility

The process of responsibility awareness entails the dissemination of knowledge to all relevant parties regarding the significance and advantages of responsibility. This encompasses the education of

employees, customers, suppliers, and the community on the responsibility activities and goals of the organization (Wan Afandi, et al., 2021).

Performance

This review discloses the various methods employed by authors to evaluate Enugu Rangers performance. The initial group conceptualised performance as the sum of all outputs produced by the individual (Abdullahi et al., 2020). Enugu Rangers performance can be defined as the comprehensive assessment of an individual's capabilities, skills and achievements within the speech. This involves evaluating how well an performance fulfils job responsibilities, meets or surpasses expectations and contributes to the organisation's overall success (Widarko & Anwarodin, 2022).

Theoretical Framework

Based on the above clarifications, the study was anchored on agenda setting theory.

Agenda Setting Theory

Agenda Setting describes a very powerful influence of the media – the ability to tell us what issues are important. Baran and Davis (2012) note that Agenda Setting Theory has its root in writing of Bernard Cohen and the works of McCombs and Shaw in 1972. Bassey (2019) posits that under the agenda setting theory, “the mass media do more than just purveyor of information.” The two basic assumptions of the theory, according to Akpan (2017) are that: the press and the media do not reflect reality; they filter and shape it, and media concentration on a few issues and subjects leads the public to perceive those issues as more important than other issues. Udoudo and Bassey (2011) assert that “agenda setting occurs when the press becomes selective in reporting the news.”

Empirical Review

Nwabuwe, et al (2022) studied mass media coverage of sports events impact and sports development in Delta State. This study sought to ascertain the extent to which mass media coverage of sports events has contributed to sports development in Delta State. The findings revealed that the mass media covers sports events in Delta State to a high extent and that the mass media has contributed to sports development in Delta State to a high extent.

Silviana, et al (2022) examined analysis of radio broadcast in Nigeria. Radio is a public medium that conveys the content of its message in the form of information, entertainment, news, and education. The qualitative research method was employed. The results obtained from this study show an in-depth analysis of the ins and outs of radio broadcasting, starting from the programs, strategies for creating programs, factors, and others.

Adeniran et al (2025) studied spatial coverage of FM radio signal variation measurement and comparison of two major radio stations, Nigeria. The parameters obtained were used to determine the coverage areas of the two FM radio stations studied in Akwa Ibom State. The obtained results showed a varied signal loss with the distance from the transmitting antenna, which is the implication of the configuration of FM radio transmitters in Akwa Ibom State.

Nwankwo (2025) studied perceived influence of social media on students academic performance as expressed by secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. This study investigated the perceived influence of social media on the academic performance of secondary school students in FCT, Abuja. A descriptive research design was adopted for the study. The findings revealed that social media has a considerable influence on the academic performance of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja.

Warnakulasuriya and Jayasinghe (2025) studied application of social media communication tools for effective internal communication in Nigeria. Alongside, it revealed the application gravity of social media platforms including WhatsApp as an emerging tool among professionals for internal communication.

Gap in Empirical Review

Some many extant literatures have been identifying and reviewed in other to change or modified the position of current study. Also, it was discovered that online advertising has no significant influence on consumer purchase behavior. None of the studies decomposed Prim sports FM coverage into level of coverage, social media instruments, sports programmes and responsibilities while performance was decomposed into physical strength, speed, endurance and agility. At the same time the study-maintained period of 2025 most current. In so doing, this study gave an empirical content to the phrase “Prime Sports FM by collecting and comparing a broader array of empirical indicators of Prime Sports FM than any study. This gap the study seeks to fill.

Methodology

The convergent mixed-method research design was deployed such as survey, unstructured interview, and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were utilized. The purpose of this design is to compare the outcomes of the quantitative and qualitative data to obtain a more complete understanding of the status, strengths and weaknesses of the Prime Sports FM over Enugu Rangers’ 2024 NPFL season campaign. Primary and secondary sources of data were deployed in line with focus of the study. In this study, the population of the study comprised all residents of Enugu State who are supporters of Rangers International Football Club of Enugu. According to 2006 census the total population of the study was 267,837. Sample size was 384. A stratified random sampling procedure was employed for selecting the participants in this study. This technique was utilized to ensure a fairly equal representation of the dependent (Ranger’s International FC performance) and independent (Enugu Prime Sports FM) variables for the study. Z test, analysis was used to test the hypotheses, determine the nature, and strength of the research variables.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSES

Table 4.1 Return Rate of Questionnaire

Respondents	Copies of Questionnaire Distributed	Copies Returned	Percentage Returned	Copies not Returned	Percentage not Returned
Residents and Supporters	384	346	90%	38	10%
Total	384	346	90%	38	10%

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1 above, shows that 346 copies of the questionnaire were duly completed and returned representing 90 percent, while 36 copies of the questionnaire were not duly completed and returned from the respondents representing 10 percent. Therefore, a total of 346 (90%) copies of questionnaire was used for analysis.

Test of Hypotheses

Tests for Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant level of coverage given by 104.9 Prime Sports FM on physical strength during Enugu Rangers’ 2024 NPFL campaign.

H_{a1}: There is significant level of coverage given by 104.9 Prime Sports FM on physical strength during Enugu Rangers’ 2024 NPFL campaign.

Table 4.2 Z – test on There is no significant level of coverage given by 104.9 Prime Sports FM on physical strength during Enugu Rangers’ 2024 NPFL campaign.

N		346
Normal Parameters	Mean	3.750
	Std Deviation	1.268
Most Extreme	Absolute	.223
Most Extreme	Positive	.223
Differences	Negative	-.210
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		20.548
Asymp. Sig.(2-tailed)		.000
a. Test distribution is Normal		
b. Calculated from data		

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value of 20.548 and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms that there was significant positive level of coverage given by 104.9 Prime Sports FM on physical strength during Enugu Rangers’ 2024 NPFL campaign.

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value of 20. 548 against the critical Z- value of 1.96 (2-tailed test at 95% level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternate hypothesis was accepted which states that there was significant positive level of coverage given by 104.9 Prime Sports FM on physical strength during Enugu Rangers’ 2024 NPFL campaign.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant level of social media instruments used by Prime Sports FM on speed during Enugu Rangers’ 2024 NPFL season.

H_{a2}: There is significant level of social media instruments used by Prime Sports FM on speed during Enugu Rangers 2024 NPFL season.

Table 4.3 Z – test on level of social media instruments used by Prime Sports FM’s on speed during Enugu Rangers’ 2024 NPFL season.

N		346
Normal Parameters	Mean	3.920
	Std Deviation	1.405
Most Extreme	Absolute	.210
Most Extreme	Positive	.210
Differences	Negative	-.192
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		22.886
Asymp. Sig.(2-tailed)		.000
a. Test distribution is Normal		
b. Calculated from data		

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z – value of 22.886 and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms that there was significant positive level of social media instruments used by Prime Sports FM's on speed during Enugu Rangers' 2024 NPFL season.

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value of 22.886 against the critical Z- value of 1.96 (2-tailed test at 95% level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternate hypothesis was accepted which states that there was significant positive level of social media instruments used by Prime Sports FM's on speed during Enugu Rangers' 2024 NPFL season.

Discussion of Findings

There was significant positive level of coverage given by 104.9 Prime Sports FM's on physical strength during Enugu Rangers' 2024 NPFL campaign ($Z= 20.548.$, $n = 346$, $.000 < 0.05$).

In result of hypothesis one, the calculated Z- value of 20. 548 against the critical Z- value of 1.96 (2-tailed test at 95% level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus the alternate hypothesis was accepted which states that there was significant positive level of coverage given by 104.9 Prime Sports FM on physical strength during Enugu Rangers' 2024 NPFL campaign. In the support of the above result in the literature Nwabuwe, Akarah and Emmanuel (2022) who studied mass media coverage of sports events impact and sports development in Delta State. The findings revealed that the mass media covers sports events in Delta State to a high extent and that the mass media has contributed to sports development in Delta State to a high extent.

There was significant positive level of social media instruments used by Prime Sports FM on speed during Enugu Rangers' 2024 NPFL season ($Z=22.886$, $n = 346$, $0.00 < 0.05$).

In result of hypothesis two, the calculated Z- value of 22.886 against the critical Z- value of 1.96 (2-tailed test at 95% level of confidence) the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus the alternate hypothesis was accepted which states that there was significant positive level of social media instruments used by Prime Sports FM on speed during Enugu Rangers' 2024 NPFL season. This is in agreement with the study by Maja, Slavko, Daria and Sandra (2019) who investigated the use of social media in communication strategies of premier league football clubs in Nigeria. Results showed that the top Premier League clubs are usually using four content formats combined with nine content types.

Summary of Findings

The findings at the end of the study include the following:

1. There was significant positive level of coverage given by 104.9 Prime Sports FM on physical strength during Enugu Rangers' 2024 NPFL campaign ($Z= 20.548.$, $n = 346$, $.000 < 0.05$). This implies that the level of coverage given by 104.9 Prime Sports FM help to expose the radio station and Enugu Rangers Football Club.
2. There was significant positive level of social media instruments used by Prime Sports FM on speed during Enugu Rangers' 2024 NPFL season ($Z=22.886$, $n = 346$, $0.00 < 0.05$). By reference is that

social media instruments help in creating more awareness across Nigeria through the help of Prime Sports FM and supporters.

Recommendations

Based on the finding, the study recommended that:

1. Enugu Prime Sports FM should open up more vistas for mass media participation while ensuring that the sports development policy would include creating more outlets for generating revenue through sports by organising more sports competitions as well as establishing more recreational outlets at the local government level.
2. Enugu Prime Sports FM should continue using social media instruments as tradition channel since it helps in passing information or awareness across Nigeria by adopting Facebook, WhatsApp, x (Twitter) etc.

Contributions to Knowledge

This study makes significant contributions to existing body of knowledge by expanding link between Enugu Prime Sports FM's coverage on Enugu Rangers International performance in the 2024 Nigeria Premier Football League.

Area Contribution

The study contributed to knowledge by covering 104.9 Prime Sports FM Enugu, Enugu State.

Methodology Contribution

The study contributed methodologically by using descriptive survey research design to run the common link between Enugu Prime Sports FM's coverage on Rangers International FC performance in the 2024 Nigeria Premier Football League.

References

- Adeniran A.O, Olabisi O and Ajao O.S. (2025) studied spatial coverage of FM radio signal variation measurement and comparison of two major radio stations within Akwa Ibom State, *Journal of VLSI Design and its Advancement*, 3(3), 1-11
- Akpan, E. S (2017). *Selected Mass Media Themes*. Jos University press, Plateau State
- Ajayi, W and Owolabi, T.(2019). *Interpretative public relations (2nd.ed.)* Spectrum books limited.
- Baran, S. J. and Davis, D. K. (2012). *Mass communication theory: Foundations, ferment and future (6thed.)*. Canada. Wadsworth Cengage Learning
- Bassey, B. E. (2019). Radio broadcast liberalisation and citizen's participation in democratic governance in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Media, Communication and Languages (JMC&L)*. A forum for research and inquiry, 6(1), 218-229.
- Camilia, N. C., Ibrahim, S. D and Dalhatu, B. L. (2023). The effect of social networking sites usage on the studies of Nigerian students. *The International Journal of Engineering and Science*, 2, 39-46
- Drapo, M. O., Godwin, E. O and Ernest-Onuiri, P. (2021). The broadcast media and sports development in Nigeria. <https://www.researchgate.net/publications>
- Enos, B. (2022). How media coverage contributes to the development of sports and esports. <https://www.enostech.com>
- Kaplan, M. A. and Haenlein, M. (2020). Users of the world unite The challenges and opportunities of social media. *Business Horizons*, 53(1), 59-68.

- Nwankwo, S.O (2025). Perceived influence of social media on students academic performance as expressed by secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.
- Nwabuwe, S. N. (2022). Perceived impact of mass media coverage of sports events on sports development in Delta State. Unpublished dissertation submitted to the postgraduate school in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of masters degree in education (M.Ed.) in sports administration and management, of the Delta State University, Abraka
- Silviana, R, Raihana, A, Bakti, H, Eric, L and Jey, R (2022). Analysis of radio broadcast, judastaipA: JurnalDakwah STAI Pariangan, 2(1), 1-23
- Udoudo, A., and Basseyy, B. E. (2011). Reporting political campaigns in Nigeria: A study of news coverage of ACN rally in Uyo by The Pioneer and The Sensor Newspapers. Journal of communication and media research. 3 (1). 41- 53.
- Wan Afandi WNH, Jamal J, and Mat Saad MZ (2021). The role of CSR communication in strengthening corporate reputation. International Journal of Modern Trends in Social Sciences, 4(17): 43-53.
- Warnakulasuriya T. and Jayasinghe C. (2025) Application of Social Media Communication Tools for Effective Internal Communication, International Journal of Business and Management Review, 13(3), 48-57
- Wu, P.Y (2024). Evaluation of the sports industry policy in china during the 2010-2024, Journal of Global Trends in Social Science, 1(2), 11-23
- Yta, E. M. (2018). Beyond watt market roundabout audiences: redesigning tourists-oriented theatres in calabar. Journal Office, 3(2), 1-22
- Yta, E. M., Umukoro, G. M and Ekpe, M. E. (2020). Increasing community discourse and action on gbv prevention in akaieffa and idundu, Cross River State. PINISI Discretion Review, 4(1), 123-134